

Animal Model w/ random effects only: IP2_animModel_1M_thin5K_x6_sigma1

FINAL MODEL No Fixed effects – USED IN MS

```
# Load model output
load(file = "IP2_animModel_1M_thin5K_x6_sigma1.RData")

### Summarize each run of model
summary(model_6chains[[1]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21595.18
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.5134  0.07514   1.427   211.9
##
##      ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam    0.1254  0.01126   0.2056    180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units      1      1      1      0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ 1
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.11128 -0.19032 -0.01501    180 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[2]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
```

```

## DIC: 21589.18
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.4944  0.03563   1.101     180
##
##           ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam    0.1281  0.03768   0.2229     180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units          1         1         1         0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ 1
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.10921 -0.19060 -0.04742     180 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[3]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21604.48
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.4346  0.04516   1.144     180
##
##           ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam    0.136  0.04275   0.2357     127.6
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units          1         1         1         0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ 1
##

```

```

##           post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp  pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.10531 -0.16764 -0.03502    88.48 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[4]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21600.23
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##           post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.4586  0.05164   1.071    180
##
##           ~dam
##
##           post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam      0.1331  0.03815   0.2184    180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##           post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units      1      1      1      0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ 1
##
##           post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp  pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.10828 -0.18204 -0.02415    224.8 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[5]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21598.95
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##           post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.4489  0.03928   1.019    180
##
##           ~dam

```

```

##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam      0.131  0.03508  0.2198      180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units      1      1      1      0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ 1
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.11108 -0.17235 -0.04108      180 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[6]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21597.28
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal      0.4323  0.02873  1.088      180
##
##      ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam      0.1367  0.05071  0.2168      180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units      1      1      1      0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ 1
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.1078 -0.1799 -0.0316      144.9 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

### Summarize 6 chains
animCh1 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[1]]$VCV)
animCh2 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[2]]$VCV)

```

```

animCh3 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[3]]$VCV)
animCh4 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[4]]$VCV)
animCh5 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[5]]$VCV)
animCh6 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[6]]$VCV)

ES_VCV_Ch1 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[1]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch2 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[2]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch3 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[3]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch4 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[4]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch5 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[5]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch6 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[6]]$VCV)

library(dplyr)

##
## Attaching package: 'dplyr'

## The following objects are masked from 'package:stats':
##
##   filter, lag

## The following objects are masked from 'package:base':
##
##   intersect, setdiff, setequal, union

resultsVCV_IP_noFE <- bind_rows(animCh1, animCh2, animCh3, animCh4, animCh5,
animCh6)
ES_VCV_IP_noFE <- bind_rows(ES_VCV_Ch1, ES_VCV_Ch2, ES_VCV_Ch3, ES_VCV_Ch4,
ES_VCV_Ch5,
  ES_VCV_Ch6)

SolCh1 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[1]]$Sol)
SolCh2 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[2]]$Sol)
SolCh3 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[3]]$Sol)
SolCh4 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[4]]$Sol)
SolCh5 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[5]]$Sol)
SolCh6 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[6]]$Sol)

ES_Sol_Ch1 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[1]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch2 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[2]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch3 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[3]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch4 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[4]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch5 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[5]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch6 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[6]]$Sol)

resultsSol_IP_noFE <- bind_rows(SolCh1, SolCh2, SolCh3, SolCh4, SolCh5,
SolCh6)
ES_Sol_IP_noFE <- bind_rows(ES_Sol_Ch1, ES_Sol_Ch2, ES_Sol_Ch3, ES_Sol_Ch4,
ES_Sol_Ch5,
  ES_Sol_Ch6)

```

```
### BELOW USED TO CHECK MIXING OF CHAINS IN PARALLEL
animalChains_IP_noFE <- cbind(animCh1, animCh2, animCh3, animCh4, animCh5,
animCh6)
names(animalChains_IP_noFE) <- c("anim1", "dam1", "unit1", "anim2", "dam2",
"unit2",
  "anim3", "dam3", "unit3", "anim4", "dam4", "unit4", "anim5", "dam5",
"unit5",
  "anim6", "dam6", "unit6")
base <- ggplot(animalChains_IP_noFE, aes(x =
as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_IP_noFE)),
  y = anim1, group = 3)) + geom_path()

base + geom_path(aes(x = as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_IP_noFE)), y =
anim2,
  group = 1), colour = "blue") + geom_path(aes(x =
as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_IP_noFE)),
  y = anim3, group = 1), colour = "green") + geom_path(aes(x =
as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_IP_noFE)),
  y = anim4, group = 1), colour = "red") + geom_path(aes(x =
as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_IP_noFE)),
  y = anim5, group = 1), colour = "orange") + geom_path(aes(x =
as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_IP_noFE)),
  y = anim6, group = 1), colour = "maroon1")
```



```
### Check autocorrs
autocorr(model_6chains[[1]]$VCV)
```

```

## , , animal
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.0000000000 -0.79769078  NaN
## Lag 5000   0.0591617116 -0.03136944  NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.0580823437  0.10007781  NaN
## Lag 50000  0.0001431442  0.04014416  NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.0829358537  0.04211960  NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0     -0.79769078  1.00000000  NaN
## Lag 5000  -0.08955807  0.03981270  NaN
## Lag 25000  0.05321935 -0.08686080  NaN
## Lag 50000 -0.01268242 -0.01048088  NaN
## Lag 250000 0.12452368 -0.12492180  NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 50000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 250000 NaN NaN  NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[2]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.0000000000 -0.83337568  NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.0124594291 -0.03211092  NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.0925786088  0.04757806  NaN
## Lag 50000  0.0351117979 -0.01845280  NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.0009337586  0.01889045  NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0     -0.833375676  1.000000000  NaN
## Lag 5000  -0.005242432  0.085390821  NaN
## Lag 25000  0.040830755  0.008698937  NaN
## Lag 50000 -0.054674486  0.027653940  NaN
## Lag 250000 0.032433303 -0.035144600  NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units

```

```

## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 50000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 250000 NaN NaN  NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[3]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##          animal      dam units
## Lag 0      1.00000000 -0.83824075  NaN
## Lag 5000   0.04049606 -0.14372387  NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.05508708  0.00399818  NaN
## Lag 50000  -0.02902165  0.01716129  NaN
## Lag 250000 0.04877504 -0.08996669  NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##          animal      dam units
## Lag 0     -0.838240754  1.00000000  NaN
## Lag 5000  -0.089972417  0.16744174  NaN
## Lag 25000  0.051210053  0.02428414  NaN
## Lag 50000  0.003469955 -0.02217744  NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.033573003  0.04926603  NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 50000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 250000 NaN NaN  NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[4]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##          animal      dam units
## Lag 0      1.000000000 -0.79657022  NaN
## Lag 5000   0.003022709 -0.01134988  NaN
## Lag 25000  0.038557158  0.09043499  NaN
## Lag 50000  0.030847007  0.01288444  NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.028053808 -0.01220941  NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##          animal      dam units
## Lag 0     -0.796570218  1.00000000  NaN
## Lag 5000   0.026413739  0.03182587  NaN

```

```

## Lag 25000 -0.041577781 -0.09295410 NaN
## Lag 50000 0.002502713 -0.01452182 NaN
## Lag 250000 0.049344705 -0.03308474 NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 50000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 250000 NaN NaN  NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[5]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.00000000 -0.814790079 NaN
## Lag 5000   0.01160412 -0.001013220 NaN
## Lag 25000  0.02096788 0.068231837 NaN
## Lag 50000 -0.06070991 0.001830111 NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.04178909 0.048435545 NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      -0.814790079 1.000000000 NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.004486404 0.021665045 NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.023501328 -0.041852963 NaN
## Lag 50000  0.080180249 -0.058128906 NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.006088750 -0.007702237 NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 50000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 250000 NaN NaN  NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[6]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.000000000 -0.76617116 NaN
## Lag 5000   0.050790772 -0.06235020 NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.040749514 -0.02131243 NaN
## Lag 50000  -0.002906688 0.01101794 NaN

```

```

## Lag 250000  0.052584037 -0.03640215  NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      -0.76617116  1.000000000  NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.04349823 -0.0065898356  NaN
## Lag 25000  0.02173967  0.0387582249  NaN
## Lag 50000  0.06243175 -0.0002405015  NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.05064096  0.0012234019  NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 50000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 250000 NaN NaN  NaN

require(QGglmm)
n <- length(resultsSol_IP_noFE$`Intercept`)
mu <- mean(resultsSol_IP_noFE$`Intercept`)
va <- mean(resultsVCV_IP_noFE$animal)
vd <- mean(resultsVCV_IP_noFE$dam)
vp <- mean(rowSums(resultsVCV_IP_noFE) - 1)

QGparams(mu = mu, var.a = va, var.p = vp, model = "binom1.probit",
closed.form = FALSE)

## [1] "Computing observed mean..."
## [1] "Computing variances..."
## [1] "Computing Psi..."

##   mean.obs  var.obs  var.a.obs  h2.obs
## 1 0.4656692 0.2488214 0.04591469 0.1845287

QGicc(mu = mu, var.comp = vd, var.p = vp, model = "binom1.probit")

## [1] "Using a semi-closed form for a binom1.probit model."

## Warning in QGicc(mu = mu, var.comp = vd, var.p = vp, model =
"binom1.probit"): Some component (var.comp.obs) are not totally
##           from a closed form solution: an integral is computed

##   mean.obs  var.obs  var.comp.obs  icc.obs
## 1 0.4656692 0.2488214  0.01306172 0.05249435

QGicc(mu = mu, var.comp = va + vd, var.p = vp, model = "binom1.probit")

## [1] "Using a semi-closed form for a binom1.probit model."

```

```

## Warning in QGicc(mu = mu, var.comp = va + vd, var.p = vp, model =
"binom1.probit"): Some component (var.comp.obs) are not totally
##           from a closed form solution: an integral is computed

##   mean.obs  var.obs var.comp.obs  icc.obs
## 1 0.4656692 0.2488214  0.06048814 0.2430986

## Heritability on Liability scale
herit_liab_IP_noFE <- resultsVCV_IP_noFE$animal/rowSums(resultsVCV_IP_noFE)
mean(herit_liab_IP_noFE)

## [1] 0.267303

HPDinterval(as.mcmc(herit_liab_IP_noFE))

##           lower      upper
## var1 0.04029596 0.5310505
## attr(,"Probability")
## [1] 0.95

#### Below is from deVillemereuil2021 (zotero) - tutorial 2, Section 4.2, p. 37

#### Heritability on Observed scale pmap_dfr is a purr function that works
#### similarly to mapply
library(purrr)
paramsB_IP_noFE <- pmap_dfr(list(mu = resultsSol_IP_noFE$(Intercept), var.a
= resultsVCV_IP_noFE$animal,
  var.p = rowSums(resultsVCV_IP_noFE) - 1), QGparams, model =
"binom1.probit",
  verbose = FALSE)
mean(paramsB_IP_noFE[["h2.obs"]])

## [1] 0.1696323

HPDinterval(as.mcmc(paramsB_IP_noFE[["h2.obs"]]))

##           lower      upper
## var1 0.02597375 0.3373421
## attr(,"Probability")
## [1] 0.95

plot(as.mcmc(resultsVCV_IP_noFE$animal))

```



```
heidel.diag(as.mcmc(resultsVCV_IP_noFE))  
  
##  
##      Stationarity start      p-value  
##      test      iteration  
## animal passed      109      0.0903  
## dam      passed      109      0.1297  
## units failed      NA      NA  
##  
##      Halfwidth Mean      Halfwidth  
##      test  
## animal passed      0.457 0.02037  
## dam      passed      0.133 0.00325  
## units <NA>      NA      NA  
  
library(coda)  
library(lattice)  
  
densityplot(as.mcmc(paramsB_IP_noFE[["h2.obs"]]))
```



```

library(ggplot2)

h2_IP_noFE <- as.data.frame(as.mcmc(paramsB_IP_noFE[["h2.obs"]]))

### FROM: https://github.com/devillemereuil/prior-
MCMCglmm/blob/master/priors.R

library(mvtnorm)
library(MCMCglmm)
library(ggplot2)
library(progress)

## ----- Prior model for monovariate

## Parameters
K <- 1e+05 # Number of iterations
nu <- 5 # nu parameter = 1000 for default prior
alpha.mu <- 0.7 # alpha.mu parameter = 0 for default prior
alpha.V <- 0.05 # alpha.V parameter = 1 for default prior

### my initial informed prior was nu=1000, alpha.mu=0.6, alpha.V=0.05 IP2 is
### nu=5, alpha.mu=0.7, alpha.V=0.05

## Prior for extended parameter Va Variance of eta
pr_var_eta <- rIW(n = K, V = diag(1), nu = nu)[, 1]
# Alpha
pr_alpha <- rnorm(K, alpha.mu, sqrt(alpha.V))

```

```
# Resulting prior on Va
pr_var_a <- (pr_alpha^2) * pr_var_eta

## Prior for residual variance Essentially useless for a binary trait, as fix
=
## 1... but keeping it in case we want to remove fix = 1
pr_var_r <- rIW(n = K, V = diag(1), nu = 1, fix = 1)[, 1]

## Resulting prior for heritability
pr_heritIP2 <- pr_var_a/(pr_var_a + pr_var_r)

## Plotting the density of the prior
qplot(x = pr_heritIP2, geom = "density")
```



```
# prior_plot library(ggpubr) figure_NoFE <- ggarrange(prior_plot, HPD_plot,
# ncol=1, nrow=2) figure_NoFE ggsave('figure_NoFE.tiff',
# figure_NoFE,width=8,height=8, bg='transparent')
```